

Results showed that the rice caseworm is highly polyphagous and could survive rice-free periods on alternative hosts. Low larval survival on rice was caused by the small volume of water used in each potted plant in the experiment. Despite this deficiency, the rice caseworm survived on 8 of 12 weed species tested. *Paspalum conjugatum* was equal to rice in survival and developmental time. *Echinochloa colona*, *E. glabrescens*, and *Cynodon dactylon* were poorer hosts than rice. Rice caseworm survived poorly on *Paspalum paspalodes* (= *distichum*), *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, and *Eleusine indica*. There was no survival on the sedges *Cyperus difformis*, *C. iria*, and *Fimbristylis miliacea* (= *littoralis*). □

Eight grasses and four sedges compared with rice as suitable plant hosts to the rice caseworm.^a IRRI, 1980.

Plant	Survival from egg to pupa (%)	Development time from egg to pupa (no. days)	Eggs laid by first-generation moths reared on plant host (no./female)
Poaceae (Gramineae)			
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	52 a	17.2 a	171
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i>	38 ab	20.0 a	177
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	28 b	18.4 a	179
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	25 b	19.4 a	153
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	25 b	18.6 a	200
<i>Paspalum paspalodes</i>	7 c	19.5 a	194
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	5 c	20.0 a	163
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i>	11 c	29.1 ab	72
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	8 c	23.8 ab	0
Cyperaceae			
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	1 c	35.0 b	—
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	0 c	—	—
<i>Cyperus iria</i>	0 c	—	—
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	0 c	—	—

^a Five replications/plant species, 20 eggs/replication. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05).

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effect of time of application and residual effect of herbicides in direct seeded flooded and rainfed banded rice

A. M. Ali and S. Sankaran, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641 003, India

Weed control experiments were conducted for four seasons at TNAU to evaluate performance of 1.0 kg butachlor/ha, 1 kg thiobencarb/ha, and 0.75 kg pendimethalin/ha individually at 8 and 12 days after seeding (DS) and in combination with 2.0 kg propanil/ha at 16 DS. Grain yield from Bhavani (see table) indicated that thiobencarb + propanil performed better than individual herbicides under flooding in both seasons. In monsoon season they produced higher yield only for rainfed banded rice. The 8th-day application of pendimethalin produced better yields than other herbicides for rainfed banded rice in summer.

In residual effect studies after rice harvest, herbicides had no adverse effect on germination and dry matter production of cotton, finger millet, blackgram, and sesamum. □

Effect of time of application of herbicides on grain yield of direct seeded rice, Coimbatore, India.

Time of application ^a	Herbicide dose (kg ai/ha)	Yield (t/ha)			
		Monsoon mean		Summer mean	
		Flooded	Rainfed banded	Flooded	Rainfed banded
8 DS					
Butachlor	1.0	3.8	3.8	4.3	2.1
Thiobencarb	1.0	4.0	3.9	4.7	2.1
Pendimethalin	0.75	4.0	4.0	4.5	2.7
12 DS					
Butachlor	1.0	4.1	3.1	4.9	1.8
Thiobencarb	1.0	4.5	2.9	5.0	1.8
Pendimethalin	0.75	4.2	3.4	4.7	2.2
16 DS					
Butachlor + propanil	1.0 2.0	5.1	3.4	5.3	1.6
Thiobencarb + propanil	1.0 2.0	5.2	3.6	5.4	1.8
Pendimethalin + propanil	0.75 2.0	4.9	3.5	5.2	2.0
Hand weeding at 20 DS		3.3	1.2	4.0	0.7
Hand weeding at 20 and 40 DS		4.9	3.7	4.7	1.8
Unweeded control		2.0	0.5	2.8	0.2
CD for time of application at rice systems		670	—	383	—
CD for rice systems at time of application		682	—	426	—

^aDS = days after seeding.